

interstore

D3.3 – Report on the Software Tool Integration with the Selected Platforms

WP3 – HESS Dimensioning, Integration and Verification of Developed Software Tools

T3.3 – Integrate software tools with selected platforms

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BMS	Battery Management System
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
ESS	Energy Storage Systems
CAN BUS	Controller Area Network bus
C&I	Commercial and Industrial sites
DEMS	Distributed Energy Management System
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DES	Distributed Energy System
DERMS	Distributed Energy Resources Management System
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EMS	Energy Management System
EV	Electrical Vehicle
FFR	Fast Frequency Regulation
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage System
HEMS	Hybrid Energy Management System
HyDEMS	Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System
INMS	Intelligent Node Management System
NILM	Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring
POD	Power Oscillation Damping
SoC	State of the Charge
SoF	State of the Function
SoH	State of the Health
SOA	State-of-the-Art
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSO	Transmission System Operator
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
VPP	Virtual Power Plant

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1 Introduction.....	7
1.1 Background	7
1.2 Objectives of the report.....	7
2 Overview of the interoperable software tool.....	8
2.1 Developments of interoperable software in WP2.....	8
2.2 Legacy protocol converter	10
3 Deployment strategies of the software tool: Options and Recommendations	11
3.1 Software Tools deployed in energy devices	11
3.2 Use aggregator NATS to communicate energy device and EMS.....	12
3.3 Local server to deploy single LPC.....	14
3.4 Dual LPC architecture	15
3.5 Direct integration energy devices with EMS	15
4 Software tool integration per platform.....	16
4.1 CyberNoc architecture in Austrian platform.....	17
4.1.1 Overview of the platforms structure with different devices	17
4.1.2 Approach used for software tool integration	18
4.1.3 Showcase of the Integration.....	18
4.2 HESStec architecture in GridLab platform in Spain.....	20
4.2.1 Introduction to the partner platform	20
4.2.2 Overview of the platforms structure with different devices	20
4.2.2.1 Grid emulator part:.....	20
4.2.2.2 HUT part:	23
4.2.3 Approach used for software tool integration	24
4.2.4 Platform-Level Software Architecture: Integration Mapping for the EMS	25
4.2.5 Showcase of the Integration with Peak shaving	27
4.3 INESctec/CapWATT architecture in Portugal platform	30
4.3.1 Introduction to the partner platform	30
4.3.2 Overview of the platforms structure with different devices	30
4.3.3 Approach used for software tool integration	30
4.3.4 Platform-Level Software Architecture: Integration Mapping for the EMS	32
4.3.5 Showcase of the Integration.....	33
4.4 E-mobility architecture for Italian platform (ENEL X).....	35
4.4.1 Introduction to the partner platform	35
4.4.2 Overview of the platforms structure with different devices	35

4.4.3	Approach used for software tool integration	36
4.4.4	Platform-Level Software Architecture: Integration Mapping for the EMS	38
4.4.5	Showcase of the Integration	42
4.5	Energy management architectures in Germany (FZJ, EATON)	46
4.5.1	Introduction to the partner platform	46
4.5.2	Overview of the platforms structure with different devices	47
4.5.3	Approach used for software tool integration	48
4.5.4	Platform-Level Software Architecture: Integration Mapping for the EMS	49
4.5.5	Showcase of the Integration	52
5	CONCLUSION.....	55
6	REFERENCES	57
7	LIST OF TABLES.....	58
8	LIST OF FIGURES.....	59

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, D3.3 – Report on the Software Tool Integration with Selected Platforms, documents the work carried out in Task T3.3 of the InterSTORE project, which focuses on the integration procedure and mapping of interoperability software tools with diverse Energy Management Systems (EMS) across multiple partner platforms. Building on the developments from WP2, where the IEEE 2030.5-based client/server library and the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) were designed and validated, this task translates those solutions into real-world deployments at the platform level. The objective is to enable seamless communication between diverse Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) and EMS platforms, overcoming the limitations of proprietary or legacy protocols while ensuring compliance with modern interoperability standards.

The report presents the technical background and capabilities of the interoperability tools, with particular emphasis on the LPC as a flexible bridging solution for different scenarios. The LPC, operating as an external protocol translator, allows existing assets using protocols such as Modbus or MQTT to participate in an IEEE 2030.5-based control ecosystem over the NATS messaging backbone. Section 2 provides an overview of these tools and their functional components, establishing the foundation for deployment planning. Section 3 outlines a range of generic deployment strategies, each offering different trade-offs between latency, resource requirements, and ease of integration. Options include deploying tools directly within energy devices, using a centralized aggregator, hosting them on a local server, or integrating them directly into EMS platforms. The advantages, disadvantages, and applicability of each approach are described to guide decision-making for diverse operational contexts. According to that, the core of this deliverable will be on section 4 where it presents the implementation of the selected deployment strategy for each partner platform, tailored to their specific technical constraints and performance requirements. For example, some partners adopted a local server approach (Option 3.3) to minimize device resource usage and maintain low-latency communication, while others integrated the tools directly into cloud-based EMS architectures. Each case includes a description of the platform architecture, integration mapping, interoperability procedures, and relevant testing or showcase results. These deployments span a variety of use cases, from hybrid energy storage systems and microgrid laboratories to large-scale C&I facilities and e-mobility infrastructures.

The work reported here demonstrates the flexibility, scalability, and adaptability of the interoperability tools developed in InterSTORE. By enabling reliable data exchange and control across diverse platforms and technologies, these solutions pave the way for advanced grid services such as flexibility provision, aggregation of distributed assets, and seamless integration into energy markets. Furthermore, the standard integration procedure and interoperability mapping developed in T3.3 provide a replicable framework for different use cases within the whole project, future deployments, supporting the broader adoption of interoperable smart grid solutions.

1 Introduction

The InterSTORE project focuses on advancing interoperability among diverse Energy Management Systems (EMS) by defining strategies, developing software tools, and implementing standardized procedures for seamless integration across various platforms. Task T3.3, led by HESStec, addresses the practical integration of these tools into selected partner platforms, ensuring reliable communication and control over heterogeneous Distributed Energy Resources (DERs). The work builds on previous developments from WP2, where the IEEE 2030.5-based client/server library and Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) were designed to bridge the gap between modern and legacy systems. By deploying these tools in real-world environments, T3.3 enables the harmonization of data exchange and control functions across EMS platforms, regardless of their underlying technologies or communication protocols.

1.1 Background

Interoperability is a key enabler for the next generation of smart grids, where DERs such as photovoltaic systems, hybrid battery storage system, EV charging stations, and flexible loads must be coordinated to deliver advanced services to the grid and energy markets. However, the diversity of communication protocols, device capabilities, and EMS architectures often leads to fragmented control systems, increasing operational complexity and limiting scalability. The IEEE 2030.5 standard provides a comprehensive, service-oriented communication framework for DER integration, while NATS offers a lightweight, low-latency messaging backbone suitable for distributed control scenarios.

In WP2, InterSTORE developed complementary approaches to achieving interoperability. One approach, native integration of the IEEE 2030.5 client/server library, enables direct adoption of the standard within EMS or device firmware. While the other proposed approach was related to deployment of the LPC which provides an external bridging solution to translate between legacy protocols (e.g., Modbus, MQTT) and IEEE 2030.5, without modifying existing device firmware. These tools were designed to be modular, platform-agnostic, and adaptable to varying deployment conditions, allowing their integration into a wide range of EMS platforms.

Task T3.3 builds upon these developments by moving the proposals to the platform-level deployment. This involves not only selecting the most appropriate integration strategy for each partner's technical and operational context but also defining a common procedure to standardize how interoperability tools are embedded in EMS architectures flexible for different use cases defined within the whole project. The aim is to ensure that diverse platforms from cloud-based aggregators to embedded industrial controllers which can achieve high levels of interoperability with minimal disruption to existing systems.

1.2 Objectives of the report

The purpose of this deliverable (D3.3) is to document the integration of the interoperability software tools developed in WP2 with the selected partner platforms, detailing the chosen deployment strategies, implementation steps, and resulting architectures. The report serves three main objectives:

1. To define and document platform with specific integration strategies, outlining how each partner has adapted the IEEE 2030.5 client/server library or LPC to its EMS environment, considering resource constraints, security requirements, and operational needs.

2. To present a standardized integration procedure – providing a repeatable methodology applicable to a broad range of EMS topologies, enabling scalability beyond the project's initial use cases.
3. To provide an interoperability mapping framework – illustrating how upper control platforms (e.g., cyberNOC, HyDEMS) can interface with hybridized and aggregated distributed energy assets for flexibility service provision.

By achieving these objectives, the report contributes to InterSTORE's goal of enabling reliable, secure, and standardized communication between heterogeneous DERs and EMS platforms. The documented integration experiences also provide valuable insights for replication in future projects and for stakeholders aiming to adopt similar interoperability frameworks.

The following sections of this report are structured as follows: Section 2 introduces briefly the interoperable software tools developed in WP2, focusing on the IEEE 2030.5 client/server library and the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC). Section 3 offers some different generic deployment options for these tools, highlighting the benefits and limitations of each option. Finally, Section 4 presents the selected deployment option and final architecture implemented by each partner platform, tailored to their specific operational requirements and constraints.

2 Overview of the interoperable software tool

The InterSTORE project has focused on advancing smart grid interoperability by developing a novel communication protocol based on the IEEE 2030.5 standard, shared over NATS messaging platform. This combination of message structure and exchange system addresses the growing need for flexible, scalable, and secure communication between different players in energy sector.

In fact, the InterSTORE project's dual-path approach to implementing IEEE 2030.5 through native library integration and external protocol conversion provides a versatile framework for enhancing interoperability in smart energy systems. This innovation not only simplifies the adoption of standardized communication protocols but also extends their applicability to legacy infrastructure, thereby accelerating the transition toward a more connected and intelligent energy ecosystem.

The main objective of the client/server and the legacy protocol converter is to enable communication between the device (client) and the EMS system (Server) over NATS messaging communication protocol and use standard IEEE 2030.5 elements to enable interoperability, scalability, loose coupling, real-time data exchange, secure and reliable communication and overcome the typical problems of existing protocols and formats, such as REST over HTTP, MQTT and ModBus.

2.1 Developments of interoperable software in WP2

In WP2 of InterSTORE project the incorporation of a new communication protocol based upon IEEE 2030.5 standard, which is shared among parties via NATS messaging broker took place. The development process was executed in two distinct phases.

The first phase focused on the creation of a comprehensive software library that encapsulates the mappings defined by the IEEE 2030.5 standard. This library serves as a foundational component for enabling native communication between distributed sources of energies, DERs, such as inverters and energy management systems. By embedding this library directly

into the operating environment of the device or system, seamless client-server communication can be achieved using the IEEE 2030.5 protocol over NATS.

Second phase is setting up (or connecting to) a NATS server. The use of NATS as the underlying messaging infrastructure offers several advantages. NATS messaging system is lightweight, highly performant, and supports secure, asynchronous communication. Its publish-subscribed model facilitates efficient data exchange between multiple endpoints, making it ideal for distributed energy applications. By leveraging NATS, the InterSTORE protocol implementation ensures low-latency, reliable communication across diverse system architectures. Additionally, NATS supports various communication scenarios, which additionally enlarge its applicability. More on communication scenarios can be found in D1.3 (https://interstore-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/D1_3_v1_00_SpecForInteroperableS-wTools_final.pdf).

To ensure successful integration of interoperability tool a thorough analysis of the target device's operating system is required. This involves evaluating the system architecture, and compatibility with the library's dependencies. The integration process must also consider the device's communication stack and security requirements. Once these parameters are understood, the IEEE 2030.5 client-server library can be embedded (and mapped), allowing the device to communicate natively using the standardized protocol.

To summarize, client/server library is integrated within the device or the energy management system (EMS). Example implementation is shown on Figure 1. The software developed in InterSTORE provides support for message payload transformation to IEEE 2030.5 using XML or JSON formats, which was added during development and is an extension of usual principle of IEEE standards.

Figure 1. Client-server architecture.

After installation of client/server tool it is possible that there are multiple EMSs to communicate between each other using the IEEE 2030.5 over NATS. This way we can satisfy much more complex communication scenarios between EMSs and field devices. An example of a complex scenario supported by client-server library shown on Figure 2.

Figure 2. Presentation of communication scenario possible via IEEE 2030.5 over NATS.

2.2 Legacy protocol converter

However, in scenarios where direct integration is not feasible—due to proprietary constraints, limited access to the device’s operating system, or legacy system limitations—the InterSTORE partners developed an alternative solution: the Legacy Protocol Converter. This converter operates externally to the device or system in a dedicated hardware and acts as a bridge between the native communication interface supported by the devices or systems and the IEEE 2030.5 protocol.

The Legacy protocol converter will act as a middleman between energy management systems and devices. The role of the legacy protocol converter is to convert messages from legacy protocols, used by devices, such as Modbus and MQTT [3.1] to protocols used by EMS, primarily NATS protocols. Legacy protocol converter will also implement schema transformations, which will allow conversion of messages between XML, JSON and Modbus. On the EMS side, IEEE 2030.5 will be fully supported with the possibility to use IEEE 2030.5 messages as XML or JSON. To function, the Legacy Protocol Converter requires a detailed inspection of the device’s message output structure. This includes identifying the data formats and control signals used by the internal legacy communication system. Once these elements are understood, they are mapped/paired each one accordingly to IEEE 2030.5 corresponding data point. Such mapping plan allows the converter to translate them into IEEE 2030.5-compliant messages, which are then transmitted via the NATS messaging platform. This approach enables systems with legacy protocols to participate in modern smart grid communication networks without requiring invasive modifications.

Figure 3. Architecture of legacy protocol converter.

Beyond its translation capabilities, the LPC is designed with scalability and modularity in mind. It can be deployed in a variety of configurations, from embedded single-board computers to rack-mounted industrial PCs, depending on the performance and environmental requirements of the deployment site. The modular software architecture allows multiple protocol adapters to run in parallel, enabling the same LPC instance to manage communications for different devices or protocol types simultaneously. This makes it especially suitable for heterogeneous energy environments, such as community microgrids or hybrid storage facilities, where equipment from multiple vendors must be managed under a unified control scheme.

Moreover, the LPC plays a critical role in supporting gradual system upgrades. The LPC allows asset owners to modernize their communication infrastructure incrementally. This ensures that flexibility services, grid-balancing functions, and advanced analytics can be deployed across both new and existing assets, preserving investments while enabling participation in emerging energy markets.

3 Deployment strategies of the software tool: Options and Recommendations

This section provides a general review of the different possible deployment strategies for the interoperability software tools developed in the InterSTORE project, namely the IEEE 2030.5 client/server library and the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC). The aim is to present a set of generic options that can be adapted to various operational contexts, depending on platform capabilities, communication requirements, and resource constraints. For each deployment option, we outline its main characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages, highlighting the trade-offs involved in terms of latency, scalability, ease of maintenance, and integration complexity.

This generic analysis serves as a reference framework that guides the selection of the most suitable approach for each partner platform, considering their specific needs, technical limitations, and targeted use cases. These are different possible options that only a subset of them has been adopted by the partners, as described in detail in Section 4. The detailed platform-specific implementations based on these options will be presented in Section 4.

3.1 Software Tools deployed in energy devices

In this deployment option, the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) systems are installed directly within the different energy devices, such as an inverter, battery controller, or hybrid energy management unit. The EMS communicates with the device through the locally running LPC and NATS, while a second NATS instance, typically deployed in the cloud, serves as the interface to an aggregator or upper-level control platform. This approach establishes a short and direct communication path between the device and the EMS, minimizing transmission delays and enabling the provision of fast grid services. Schematic of this architecture is presented in Figure 4.

Advantages:

The primary benefit of this method is the low latency between the device and the EMS, making it particularly well-suited for time-critical services such as Fast Frequency Response (FFR), virtual inertia, and peak shaving. Since data transformation occurs locally within the device, only one conversion step is required, reducing complexity and the potential for data inconsistencies. Additionally, this architecture simplifies troubleshooting by keeping the entire communication and processing pipeline confined to a single hardware unit.

Figure 4. Architecture 1: LPC with multiple energy devices with two NATS.

Limitations:

The main challenge in this approach lies in the resource requirements of the LPC and NATS. Running these processes on an energy device may demand additional processing power, memory, and storage, which are often limited in embedded systems. In some cases, the device's operating system may not support the necessary software environment (e.g., Java runtime or Docker containers), making deployment infeasible without hardware upgrades. This can increase both integration costs and maintenance efforts, especially if the device firmware requires modification to host the additional components.

This option is most applicable in scenarios where the device already possesses sufficient computational resources and supports the required runtime environments. It is also well-suited for new-generation devices designed with interoperability in mind, allowing them to host additional services without compromising performance.

By deploying the software tools within the device itself, the communication loop remains extremely short, enabling near real-time control actions. However, this advantage must be balanced against the practical constraints of device hardware and firmware capabilities, as well as the increased maintenance responsibility associated with updating software components embedded in critical field equipment.

3.2 Use aggregator NATS to communicate energy device and EMS

In this deployment strategy, as shown in Figure 5, a single NATS messaging server—typically hosted in the cloud—acts as the central communication hub between energy devices and the Energy Management System (EMS). While several LPCs will be used for each energy devices. Both the devices and the EMS connect to this shared NATS instance, enabling bidirectional data exchange without the need for multiple NATS deployments. The same NATS server can also facilitate integration with an aggregator or upper-level control platform, simplifying the overall architecture by consolidating communication channels into a single point.

Advantages:

The main advantage of this approach is its simplicity and reduced infrastructure footprint. By operating only one NATS instance, system maintenance and monitoring are significantly streamlined. This architecture also reduces the computational load on the energy devices, as they do not need to run a local NATS server—only the necessary communication client. This makes the option particularly attractive for devices with limited processing capabilities or constrained operating environments. Additionally, the centralized NATS server provides a

straightforward mechanism for integrating multiple EMS instances or third-party aggregators without additional local deployment.

Figure 5. Architecture 2: Single NATS messaging with multiple LPC within the devices.

Limitations:

The primary limitation of this model is the increased communication latency compared to local or embedded deployments. Since all data must travel to and from the cloud-hosted NATS server, real-time responsiveness may be affected, particularly in use cases requiring sub-second control actions such as Fast Frequency Response or virtual inertia emulation. Furthermore, system reliability becomes more dependent on the stability of the internet connection. Any network disruption between the device and the cloud server can result in delays or loss of control messages. Also, the device may not support Java or Docker to deploy LPC. Another consideration is security: because communication is routed through an external server, robust encryption and authentication mechanisms are essential to ensure data integrity and prevent unauthorized access. However, it is worth noting that IEEE 2030.5 inherently includes strong security provisions, such as the use of Certificate Authority (CA)-based authentication, which significantly enhances trust and protection within the communication framework. These built-in mechanisms can mitigate some of the risks associated with cloud-based communication, although careful configuration and certificate management remain necessary.

This deployment option is best suited for scenarios where ultra-low latency is not a critical requirement, and where the devices have limited processing resources. It is particularly relevant for distributed systems where multiple devices must be monitored and controlled through a common platform, and where centralizing communication management provides operational efficiency.

By centralizing communication in a single NATS instance, this approach achieves simplicity and scalability, at the cost of higher latency and dependence on cloud connectivity. For many applications, especially those involving monitoring, non-critical control, or aggregated data

analysis, this trade-off can be entirely acceptable, making this option a good and practical choice in resource-limited environments.

3.3 Local server to deploy single LPC

In this deployment option, the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) and a local NATS instance are installed on a dedicated local LAN server like the Energy Management System (EMS) and the energy devices. The local NATS handles all communication between the LPC and the EMS, enabling low-latency, secure, and reliable message exchange for operational control and monitoring.

In parallel, a second NATS instance—typically deployed in the cloud—is used to integrate the local EMS with an external aggregator or upper-level control platform. This dual NATS arrangement allows the local loop (devices–LPC–EMS) to operate independently of the cloud connection, ensuring that critical control functions remain operational even if internet connectivity is lost, while still enabling data sharing and control coordination with remote systems when available.

This architecture is particularly useful in scenarios where the EMS needs to maintain fast, on-site decision-making while also participating in aggregated flexibility services, such as demand response or virtual power plant operations. The schematic of this architecture is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Architecture 3: Single LPC with multiple NATS.

Advantages:

The main advantage of this approach is that it combines low latency and high reliability for local services such as peak shaving, fast frequency response or virtual inertia, with the flexibility to participate in aggregated services. Devices need less resources and as the devices are not required to run Docker, Java or NATS, their computational load remains minimal. In addition, the architecture is modular, making it straightforward to connect additional devices to the local NATS without affecting the aggregator link.

Limitations:

The main limitation is the need for both a local server and a cloud-hosted NATS, which increases infrastructure and configuration complexity. Proper topic routing between the two NATS instances is important to prevent message duplication or delays. Despite these challenges, this option provides a balanced solution for platforms requiring fast on-site decision-making while maintaining interoperability with external aggregators.

3.4 Dual LPC architecture

In the dual LPC architecture, two instances of the LPC are placed between the energy devices and the EMS, connected through a shared NATS server. One LPC is positioned on the device side to translate the legacy protocol used by the DERs, such as Modbus or MQTT, into IEEE 2030.5 messages over NATS. The second LPC is positioned on the EMS side to perform the reverse translation from IEEE 2030.5 to the protocol understood by the EMS. In most implementations, each LPC runs on its own local hardware close to the system it serves, meaning the “local server” is essentially on both sides — one near the devices, and another at the EMS location — so that neither end needs to natively support IEEE 2030.5.

Figure 7. Architecture 4: Dual LPC with single NATS.

Advantage:

This approach makes it possible to apply the InterSTORE interoperability concept even when neither the DERs nor the EMS can be modified to support IEEE 2030.5 directly. It enables structured, standardised data exchange between otherwise incompatible systems, improves scalability through the NATS publish/subscribe model, and allows integration of heterogeneous protocols without changing the original firmware of the devices or EMS.

Limitation:

The main drawback is the increased complexity and cost of managing two LPC instances instead of one. Synchronisation between the two converters and careful management of NATS topics is necessary to avoid errors and ensure consistent data flows. Nevertheless, the dual LPC setup is a practical solution for complex environments where both ends of the control chain rely on legacy or proprietary communication protocols.

3.5 Direct integration energy devices with EMS

In this deployment option, the EMS natively implements the IEEE 2030.5 protocol and communicates directly with the energy devices, removing the need for a local LPC or a local NATS server. A single cloud-based NATS instance can be used for integration with an external aggregator, enabling upper-level coordination and market participation. This option is added in this sub-section only for comparative purpose and also to provide an alternative solution due to installation limits if needed. The general schematic of this option is presented in Figure 8.

Advantages:

The advantage of this approach is its simplicity and speed. By eliminating the local LPC and

NATS, the communication chain between the devices and the EMS is shortened, reducing latency and minimising the number of components to maintain. It is particularly suitable for scenarios where the EMS is programmable, supports direct protocol integration, and can host IEEE 2030.5 services without compromising performance.

Figure 8. Architecture 5: Direct integration of EMS and energy devices with cloud NATS.

Limitations:

The main limitation is that it requires the EMS to be adapted or extended to handle IEEE 2030.5 directly, including the development and maintenance of data adapters. This increases software complexity within the EMS and may demand more powerful hardware. EMS should be programmable and maintained. Additionally, without a local NATS, all aggregator interactions depend on a stable internet connection. Despite these constraints, direct integration remains an attractive option where the EMS platform is flexible and designed to support standardised communication protocols natively.

4 Software tool integration per platform

This section forms the core of the report, presenting the final implementation and integration of the interoperability software tools at the platform level for each partner. It details how the IEEE 2030.5 client/server library and the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) have been deployed within different Energy Management System (EMS) architectures, adapted to the specific requirements, constraints, and operational contexts of each platform.

For each partner platform, the section includes the final architectural diagram, an interoperability mapping, and a description of the methodology used for deployment, configuration, and testing. The integration level is shown from the highest layer—aggregator or upper control platform—down to the EMS and, where relevant, the conversion layer interfacing with field devices.

The interoperability maps are designed to support upper-level control platforms such as CyberNoc, HyDEMS, HEMS, and e-mobility systems in achieving hybridisation and aggregation of distributed energy resources. This enables the provision of flexibility services, real-time monitoring, and coordinated control across heterogeneous assets.

The section also highlights the specific role of the interoperability tools in each deployment, the strategy applied for integrating them, and any limitations or challenges encountered during implementation. By documenting these platform-level integrations in detail, this section provides both a reference for replication in similar contexts and a benchmark for evaluating the performance of the proposed solutions in real operational environments.

4.1 CyberNoc architecture in Austrian platform

CyberNoc is a flexibility management platform developed by CyberGrid that offers a systematic approach towards aggregating different DERs and generating balancing services from pooled resources [3.2]. Its architecture is built from stand-alone micro services, which give it a resilience and scalability. During InterSTORE project CyberNoc was upgraded with IEEE 2030.5 client-server library as well as other micro services, which are in more detail presented in D4.1. On the Figure 9 we can observe how client-server library is integrated as Interoperability toolkit. The micro service architecture of CyberNoc also monitors the important connections inside the system as well as automatic scalability of the service.

Figure 9. Systematic representation of integration of client-server library in CyberNoc.

4.1.1 Overview of the platforms structure with different devices

CyberGrid contributes to the InterSTORE project with its advanced Energy Management System (EMS) platform, CyberNoc, hosted in the AWS cloud. Within the project, CyberNoc connects to 20 distributed energy devices—including solar panels and battery storage systems—belonging to the Energy Community Dietach. To ensure secure and reliable communication, each household is linked to CyberNoc via a private mobile network, isolating data traffic from public internet exposure, as shown on Figure 9. This setup enables real-time monitoring and control of energy assets, supporting the community's transition to a smarter, more resilient energy infrastructure.

While connecting 20 field devices we must note that they are of various types, sizes and date of manufacturing, which all adds to the complexity of setting up the connections. More on this can be found in report D5.2 (<https://interstore-project.eu/resources/>).

4.1.2 Approach used for software tool integration

CyberGrid follows direct option of software tool integration by installing client-server library inside CyberNoc architecture. This approach is preferred as CyberGrid wants to showcase real life value of the newly developed protocol, test its pros and cons and find appropriate enhancements for the future use in CyberNoc and other EMS systems. From there energy community members and their devices, which are part of Austrian pilot and are participating in UC1 and UC2 of InterSTORE project, will be monitored and controlled by implementing LPC on IoTmaxx device, serving as hardware, at each household location. NATS server is installed inside AWS, which is on one side a limitation as this prevents outside parties to participate in communication channel but on the other side it serves as an additional security measure as CyberGrid is researching data collection from private individuals and cannot afford to have a data breach. CyberNoc will be deployed on a cloud in parallel to NATS server. The proposed architecture is very similar to option 2 of deployment methods on section 3 but with some adaptation on the location of EMS for practical implementation. The schematic overview is presented on the Figure 10.

Figure 10. High level architecture of client-server library and LPC in Austrian pilot

4.1.3 Showcase of the Integration

The detailed integration steps for installing client-server library inside CyberNoc are presented in D4.1, while installation procedures at each energy community member household is detailed in D5.2. To summarise, in order to have a working communication (so called Full Chain Channel - FCC), presented on Figure 11 the next criteria must be met:

1. CyberNoc instance is running.
2. Client-server library is successfully integrated in CyberNoc.
3. IoTmaxx device hosting LPC is installed in a household.

4. Between AWS network, which is hosting CyberNoc, and LPC in IoTmaxx a Private Mobile Network (APN) is established.
5. IoTmaxx connects to devices (solar panels and/or battery) in the household.
6. LPC is correctly set up to map from legacy protocol to IEEE 2030.5 and vice-versa.

Figure 11. Presentation of FCC in Austrian Pilot.

A presentation of working FCC can be seen on Figure 12, where CyberNoc UI shows incoming data points from a connected solar panel.

Figure 12 Solar panel data gathered via FCC in CyberNoc.

4.2 HESStec architecture in GridLab platform in Spain

4.2.1 Introduction to the partner platform

The Spanish GridLab facility, located in Valencia and operated in collaboration with key project partners, serves as a real-world environment for validating advanced energy management systems under representative grid conditions [3.3]. Designed for high configurability and hardware-in-the-loop integration, the lab enables the safe testing of distributed control strategies, converter-based generation systems, and hybrid energy storage units in both islanded and grid-connected configurations.

GridLab supports the platform used for a wide range of use cases, with UC4 and UC7 being a prominent scenario that tests fast services like virtual inertia, peak shaving as well as black start capabilities, autonomous operation, and seamless reintegration with the external grid which will be reported within WP4 and WP5 deliverables. The facility enables real-time monitoring, fast data acquisition, and remote supervisory control, making it ideal for validating functionalities such as voltage dip detection, automatic transfer switching (ATS), and system resilience under fault conditions. It plays a crucial role in demonstrating the full stack integration of HyDEMS, acting as the operational backbone for WP5.

4.2.2 Overview of the platforms structure with different devices

The advanced platform in GridLab will allow HESStec to have a testing environment to check and analyze the behavior of the devices in different emulated networks. This laboratory is capable of emulating variations in frequency and voltage of the network; a renewable generation source or a source of energy consumption. The schematic of the location of components within the GridLab is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. GridLab equipment distribution

The laboratory is made up of several cabinets with various functions, we can see a diagram of the operation in Figure 13.

4.2.2.1 Grid emulator part:

The PCS1 and PCS2 converters will function as rectifier and inverter, respectively, in order to decouple the commercial electrical network from that of the network that will be emulated in the laboratory. They will be connected to the high-level EMS.

Four power converters (also known as PCS, that is bidirectional rectifiers/inverters), of the FS4G type, have been installed on the bench. These cabinets are capable of converting alternating current to direct current and vice versa. Two of the four cabinets (PCS1, PCS2) will be in charge of transforming the service network current from AC to DC. In other words, both

converters will work as synchronous rectifiers, transforming from the 400V AC of the network to 800-850V DC.

On the other hand, the PCS3 and PCS4 converters will transform the direct current that comes from the UGRID to alternating current or vice versa depending on the needs of the work to be carried out. One of them, specifically the PCS4, will work as a grid forming voltage source so we can control the voltage and frequency. Thus being able to emulate voltage drops or surges and see how the systems under test react.

The PCS3 will function as either a programmable grid following load or a programmable grid following source. This will be defined by the power flow;

- If the power flow goes from direct to alternating, the FS4G (PCS) will work as a grid following source, that is, it will act as a renewable generator such as a wind or solar source. A recirculation of power will be generated between the converters on the left.
- If the power flow is from AC to DC, the FS4G (PCS) will work as a programmable load. A recirculation of power will be generated between the converters on the left.

FS4G converters are a flexible AC/DC converter designed fully by HESStec' team. Those converters were designed for energy storage grid integration (FS4G = Fast Storage For Grid), and has multiple operation modes:

- They can work as a simple synchronous rectifier, ensuring the PF=1 at PoC (Is the case of the FS4G #1 & 2). They can work also as grid following converters (is the case of FS4G #3) working at full four quadrants, able to receive different P&Q references in real time, that in this case this system can work both as a emulated grid source (such as PV or Wind) working under a defined power profile, or as a variable load.

- This system has also the ability for working as a grid forming inverter (FS4G #4). In this case it has also three different operation modes:

o Fixed voltage and frequency voltage source. It works under a defined Fout and Vout parameters, that could be modified online and helps us for creating controlled grid events.

o Synchronous Voltage source, it works as a synchronous generator with a defined f/P and V/Q droops but always synchronized with an existing grid.

o Synchronous generator, it works as a synchronous generator with a defined f/P and V/Q droops that can works either with another existing or not voltage source. This mode helps us for creating different weakness levels of a grid, from a quite stiff grid under power oscillations or power steps or a quite unstable grid under those events, just modifying the droops values. All these converters connected by the common dc-link allow us for creating different grid scenarios, recirculating the energy. In summary, the function that each FS4G converter will perform, all of them 250 kW power modules, is shown in the following table:

Table 1: Main PCS of grid emulation in GridLab

PCS	Function
PCS1	Bidirectional AC/DC rectification function.
PCS2	Bidirectional AC/DC rectification function.
PCS3	According to the power flow: - Programmable charging function grid following. - Programmable source function grid following.
PCS4	Voltage source function grid forming.

In general, as shown Figure 15 and Figure 14, the GridLab can be divided to two main parts which are the HUT part and the grid emulation part. HUT (HESS Under Test) is consisting of Hybrid system with its intelligent management system while the grid emulator shown in Figure 14 is consisting of four PSC of FS4G type, for managing different type of faults and scenarios. As can be seen in both figures, one UCAP is for grid emulator side, is only the DC link part of the grid emulator converters. and the other UCAP (the one of the project interest) is located in Figure 2 next to HESS under test system.

Figure 14. Real system scheme

4.2.2.2 HUT part:

Figure 15. HESS Under Test (HUT) configuration

AC/DC DER1 converter:

The grid-forming converter, used as the device in this task, is a high-performance AC/DC power converter capable of operating in grid-forming mode. It provides autonomous voltage and frequency control and is responsible for maintaining grid stability even in weak or islanded grid conditions. Designed to support hybrid energy storage configurations, this converter also allows for real-time bidirectional power exchange with the EMS and other devices in the system. Its advanced control features make it ideal for testing IEEE 2030.5 protocol implementation and system-level services like virtual inertia, black start, and power oscillation damping.

UCAP:

The high-power UCAP system integrated into the GridLab is rated at 300 kW with a 60-second energy capacity (equivalent to 18 MJ). This device provides ultra-fast response capabilities for power smoothing, frequency support, and transient management. While not directly communicating with the LPC during this task, it is electrically interfaced with the grid-forming converter and plays a crucial role in dynamic power testing, system response evaluations, and real-time stress scenarios.

BATTERY:

The lithium-ion battery energy storage system included in the AGL setup has a rated capacity of 250 kW / 250 kWh. It provides sustained energy delivery for load shifting, peak shaving, and longer-duration power support services. Like the UCAP, the battery is managed by the same AC/DC grid-forming converter, enabling coordinated hybrid operation. Although the LPC integration in this task focuses specifically on the converter's communication with the EMS, the battery's participation in system behavior remains essential during testing and validation phases.

4.2.3 Approach used for software tool integration

In this section, the deployment scenario approach used for the LPC, derived from the experiences and requirements of project for Spanish pilot is presented. The scenario highlights flexible approach to integrating LPC in diverse environments, ensuring seamless communication between legacy systems and modern energy management frameworks while adhering to the IEEE 2030.5 standard. It will present a standard and common procedure that clearly defined how to integrate the interoperability software tools in an energy management system platform useful for Spanish GridLab.

The selected integration approach for interoperability of software tools within the Energy Management System is similar to option 3 presented in section 3.3 of this report. Where it is deploying the tools on a local server. This configuration enables seamless interaction between different applications while ensuring data security and low-latency communication. The justification for selecting this option will be provided in the following:

- **Resource Efficiency:** By deploying the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) and NATS on a local server, we reduce the resource burden on individual energy devices. This ensures that devices do not need to support Docker, Java, or NATS, which can be resource-intensive.
- **Reduced Device Complexity:** Energy devices in our grid lab will not need to run additional processes, simplifying their operation and reducing potential points of failure.
- **Optimized Communication:** The converter and EMS are located within the same LAN, allowing for faster communication compared to cloud-based solutions. Deploying the NATS server locally ensures lower latency and better performance.
- **Easier Deployment and Maintenance:** We want to free our converter and EMS from the difficulty of deploying Docker on an embedded device and having to reserve resources to keep the LPC server and NATS running.

In fact, by choosing option of section 3.3. the following limitations from other options are addressed:

- **Memory Limitations:** By offloading processes to a local server, we mitigate memory and processing power constraints on energy devices.
- **Ease of Deployment:** The local server setup allows for easier maintenance and updates of the LPC and NATS, as they are centralized rather than distributed across multiple devices.

Comparison with Other Options:

- **Option 1, where the software tools deployed in energy devices:** This approach offers low latency but requires energy devices to run additional software, potentially exceeding their resource capacities.
- **Option 2, aggregator NATS used to communicate energy device and EMS:** While resource-efficient, this option introduces significant delays due to cloud-based communication, which is not suitable for our real-time energy management needs.

- Option 5, where a direct integration of energy devices with EMS is used: This provides the fastest communication but requires extensive modification of the EMS to support IEEE 2030.5 and maintain data adapters, increasing complexity and maintenance efforts.

Integration Approach:

The main goal of the integration for this partner is to ensure seamless interoperability between energy devices and the EMS while maintaining fast response with high performance and resource efficiency.

Objectives:

- Deploy LPC and NATS on a local server to offload processing from energy devices.
- Ensure minimal latency in data communication to meet the real-time demands of the energy management system. This is the most important objective of Spanish use cases within the project as the fast high-power services will be tests in UC4 and UC7 using this proposed architecture to reduce latency while reading the signals from devices.
- Facilitate easy maintenance and scalability of the system.

Service Deployment:

- Local server: Deploy LPC and NATS on a dedicated local server.
- Possibility of cloud integration: Utilize a secondary NATS in the cloud for future possibility of having an aggregator for integration if needed.

Communication Protocols:

- IEEE 2030.5: Standard for device communication and data transformation.
- NATS: Messaging system to ensure reliable and low-latency data transfer.
- Modbus custom protocol that energy device used for communicating with LPC.

Standard Procedure for Integration:

1. Local Server Setup: Configure a local server within the LAN to host the LPC and NATS services.
2. Device Connection: Connect energy devices to the local server via LAN for data exchange.
3. Protocol Conversion: Implementation and parametrization of the LPC on the local server to convert device-specific data to IEEE 2030.5 standard.
4. Data Publishing: Implementation of NATS connector in EMS for LPC and publishing the converted data to the NATS topic for consumption by the EMS.
5. Aggregator Integration: Deploy a secondary NATS instance in the cloud to facilitate data sharing with external aggregators.
6. Monitoring and Maintenance: Establish monitoring tools and maintenance schedules to ensure the local server and services are running optimally.

As the summary, option 3.3 from previous chapter is the best fit for our platform due to its balance between resource efficiency, ease of deployment, and performance. By offloading critical processes to a local server, we ensure that energy devices operate efficiently without additional resource strain while maintaining an effective and flexible data communication architecture. This approach frees our converter and EMS from the complexities of deploying Docker on embedded devices and leverages the speed of LAN communications to optimize performance.

4.2.4 Platform-Level Software Architecture: Integration Mapping for the EMS

This sub-section presents the detailed software architecture implemented in the GridLab platform, (shown on Figure 16) focusing on the allocation and interaction of the interoperability software tools within the Energy Management System (EMS) environment. It describes how the IEEE 2030.5 client/server components and the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) are

integrated at different layers of the control chain, from device-level communication to upper-platform coordination. The mapping illustrates the flow of data between the hybrid energy storage system, the EMS, and the aggregator interface, highlighting the role of both the local NATS server for low-latency operations and the cloud-based NATS for remote integration.

Figure 16 Mapping in Spanish Gridlab scenario.

Mapping Strategy for Integration and Deployment of Software Tool Package:

Network Configuration:

All devices are connected via a private Local Area Network (LAN) through a central router, using Ethernet (RJ45) cabling. This setup ensures secure and stable communication between devices and the EMS. When cloud services are required, the connection is established via the internet.

Deployment Process:

1. **Local Server Deployment:** The integration process begins with deploying the interoperability tools on a local server running a Linux-based operating system. This server hosts the key components inside Docker containers:
 - Container 1: NATS messaging server.
 - Container 2: Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC).
2. **Creation of NATS connector using TLS:** A dedicated NATS connectors are created, supporting both TLS-secured connections for cloud integration and non-TLS connections for local communication between the EMS (HyDEMS) and energy devices. To ensure stability, the connector undergoes a 24-hour test for local connections, using an LTE router to verify reconnection behavior in the event of a NATS server outage or network disruption.
3. **Data Flow and Protocol conversion:** Following deployment, the system undergoes functional testing:
 - Generic Data Flow: Validated using NATS servers.
 - IEEE 2030.5 Data Flow: Verified for correct format and compatibility.
 - Power Converter Device (Danfoss) Integration: The Danfoss system communicates with the LPC via its native Modbus protocol. The LPC converts this data to IEEE 2030.5 format and publishes it to the appropriate NATS topic.

Therefore, as shown in Figure 17, the Single LPC integration scenario, as implemented by HESStec, focuses on deploying a single LPC for bidirectional communication between a grid-forming (GFM) power converter as a device used in this part of the project and an EMS. This approach ensures seamless data exchange while adhering to the IEEE 2030.5 standard, en-

abling real-time monitoring and control of grid-forming converters. The LPC acts as a protocol translator, converting the proprietary Modbus protocol used by the power inverter into the standardized IEEE 2030.5 protocol required by the EMS, and vice versa. In this scenario, the LPC is deployed within the device's local network using a virtual machine that hosts two Docker containers: one for the LPC and another for a local NATS message queue server. The NATS server acts as an intermediary, ensuring reliable bidirectional communication between the LPC and other system components. This setup allows the LPC to efficiently manage data transformations in both directions, enabling the EMS (INMS in Figure 17) to read real-time data from the inverter (e.g., active power) and send control setpoints (e.g., power targets) to the inverter. As shown in this architecture, the EMS/INMS here will communicate with the Grid-Forming (GFM) device which has a hybrid system (UCAP and batteries) and with other elements that emulate a grid.

The use of a single LPC instance avoids redundancy and enhances operational efficiency, making it a cost-effective solution for integrating legacy devices into modern energy management systems. As reported in D3.2 [3.4], performance evaluation of the Single LPC setup was conducted through speed tests, which measured delays under varying conditions such as polling rates, the number of data points, and CPU usage. These tests confirmed the system's ability to handle real-time data exchange with minimal latency, a critical requirement for fast power services. The results demonstrated that the Single LPC configuration is well-suited for scenarios where a single point of translation is sufficient, providing a robust and scalable solution for integrating legacy grid components with modern energy management frameworks. The proposed architecture is flexible to multiple use cases, supporting both standalone and aggregated operation modes. In particular, it can operate without an aggregator in UC4, while UC7 will have the possibility of integrating an aggregator if required.

Figure 17. Final data communication scheme in GridLab.

4.2.5 Showcase of the Integration with Peak shaving

In this section, the results of the integration and validation tests conducted for the single LPC architecture are presented in the advanced grid laboratory located in Valencia, Spain. The tests focus on evaluating the performance of the proposed LPC solution in handling a fast service known as Fast Peak Shaving (FPS). This service was used to assess the system's capability to manage high-power, real-time operations, ensuring that the LPC could effectively support rapid and dynamic grid responses. The results demonstrate the LPC's ability

to handle fast power services with minimal latency, validating its suitability for real-time, high-performance grid applications. The deployment in the advanced grid lab in Spain, as illustrated in section 4.2.2 (shown in Figure 18), consists of two main sections. On the right side, the Hybrid Energy Storage System (HESS) under test is depicted, which includes a storage element and a GFM converter. On the left side, the figure shows elements that emulate a weak grid, and renewable profile are presented, incorporating various DERs to simulate real world grid conditions. The system parameters are detailed in section 4.2.2. This configuration allows for the evaluation of the LPC's performance in managing fast power services under realistic grid scenarios.

The goal of the FPS test is to evaluate the capability of the developed energy management tool, integrated with the LPC, to regulate and fix the power at the Point of Connection (POC). The test involves applying a load step change and measuring the transient response at the POC. The LPC-based solution is tasked with stabilizing the power at the POC by dynamically adjusting the power output using the energy management tool and provided power capacity from the storage element shown in Figure 18. Additionally, the power measurement signals obtained through the LPC approach are compared with those from the CAN-based approach to assess the accuracy and responsiveness of the LPC in handling fast power services.

This test validates the LPC's ability to support real-time grid management and its effectiveness in maintaining grid stability during rapid load changes. The test is created by two step load change. The first one will decrease the power flow at the POC up to 40 kW and after 60 seconds it will be removed and back to its previous value. The measured power flow at the POC with FPS control with different approaches is presented and compared in Figure 19 and Figure 20. After activation, the FPS control is expected to compensate the variation of power by HESS system and therefore, hold the power flow at the POC around its pre-defined value. The compared results of this test demonstrate that, the FPS was able to successfully manage the power flow at the POC, with a fast reaction time (around 150 ms). The fast reaction time has been achieved with proper tuning of the designed controller for the peak shaving service. The dynamic reaction of GFM converter, was achieved thanks to fast active power/current absorption/injection from the storage elements shown in Figure 19. According to the obtained results, at the beginning, when the power step at the POC is happening, the active power from HESS starts to decrease by absorbing the active power (charging the storage system) to compensate for the changes at the POC.

One of the key performance indicators (KPIs) defined for this service was the time response. After calculation and comparing the results shown in Figure 20 for the CAN-based and LPC-based approaches, it was determined that the LPC can achieve a time response of approximately 250 ms. This value falls within an acceptable range, demonstrating the LPC's capability to effectively support fast, high-power services such as Fast Peak Shaving. It is worth mentioning that the selected time window for assessing the fast service is designed to encompass a wide range of high-power, fast-response applications such as Fast Frequency Response (FFR), virtual inertia emulation, and Power Oscillation Damping (POD). Notably, many Transmission System Operators (TSO), including those in Europe, use a 500 ms window for the calculation of the Rate of Change of Frequency (RoCoF), which serves as a common metric for assessing dynamic stability services. In this context, a full system response within 250 ms is well within the acceptable range for compliance with such requirements.

Moreover, it is worth highlighting that the initial converter-based system response is triggered in less than 5 ms, allowing the system to start reacting almost instantaneously, while the full dynamic response stabilizes within the 250 ms window. This demonstrates the suitability of the proposed architecture for practical deployment in real-world scenarios requiring fast and reliable grid support.

Figure 18 Testing Scenario – FPS.

Figure 19. Laboratory experimental results of FPS service: Power at the POC and storage output power

Figure 20. Laboratory experimental results: comparisons of controller power at the POC: CAN-based method and LPC-based approach.

4.3 INESctec/CapWATT architecture in Portugal platform

4.3.1 Introduction to the partner platform

This demonstration at the platform level will be part of the UC05, where we have a hybrid storage system (Lithium + Vanadium) installed at Capwatt premises in Portugal [3.5], with an EMS that is running in a local PC with a LabView environment, which is providing the dispatch to the batteries according to an optimization algorithm. The inverter of the second life Lithium battery is the equipment that will be the focus of the demo. It is now communicating with the EMS via ModBus TCP/IP and the data monitoring will be done in a parallel communication via IEEE 2030.5.

4.3.2 Overview of the platforms structure with different devices

The demonstration specified in use case 05, makes use of several assets and systems in order to deploy the IEEE 2030.5 LPC. These can be summarized as follows:

- Computer - PC;
 - AMD Ryzen Threadripper PRO 3945WX processor (12C/24T, 4.0/4.3GHz, 6MB L2/64MB L3)
 - RAM 16 GB RDIMM DDR4-3200 ECC
 - Hard disk
 - 512 GB SSD M.2 2280 PCIe 4.0 NVMe Opal
 - 1000 W platinum power supply
 - Optical drive 9.0 mm DVD±RW
 - Dimensions (Width x Depth x Height) 165 x 460 x 446 mm
 - Weight Net: 24kg
 - Color Black
- Windows 11 operating system with internet connection hosting LabView for dispatch of the battery and hosting the LPC as well as docker hub
- NATS local server installed on the local PC
- Inverter - Ingecon Sun 3 Play 100TL (details on Figure 21)

4.3.3 Approach used for software tool integration

For the integration of the Interoperability Software Tools and considering the benefits and limitations of the deployment options presented in Section 3, option 3.3 has been selected for implementation. This choice is based on the following reasons:

- Single Point Deployment: Simplifies setup with one EMS and one inverter.
- No Asset Aggregation: Eliminates the need for a shared NATS cloud.
- Infrastructure Compatibility: Existing systems lack native IEEE 2030.5 support, requiring LPC.
- Co-Location: EMS and inverter are in the same physical space.
- Flexible Hardware: The installed PC is flexible enough for the installation of the LPC without the need of additional hardware
- Resource Efficiency: By deploying the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) and NATS on a local server, we reduce the resource burden on individual energy devices. This ensures that additional devices do not need to support Docker, Java, or NATS, which can be resource-intensive.
- Optimized Communication: Co-locating LPC and EMS ensures faster, low-latency communication compared to cloud solutions, reducing complexity.

INGECON SUN STORAGE 3Play Serie TL

100TL	
Valores de Entrada de Batería (DC)	
Rango de tensión ⁽¹⁾	627 - 850 V
Tensión máxima ⁽²⁾	1.100 V
Potencia máxima de carga / descarga	60 kW / 100 kW
Corriente máxima de carga / descarga	111 A / 185 A
Tipo de batería	Ion-Liño, plomo
Corriente de cortocircuito	240 A
Comunicación con el BMS (Battery Management System)	CAN Bus 2.0 / Ethernet
Valores de Salida (AC)	
Potencia nominal	100 kW
Máx. temperatura a potencia nominal ⁽³⁾	50 °C
Corriente máxima	145 A
Tensión nominal	400 V
Frecuencia nominal	50 / 60 Hz
Factor de Potencia	1
Factor de Potencia ajustable	Sl. S _{máx} =100 kVA Q _{máx} =60 kVAR
THD	<3%
Rendimiento	
Eficiencia máxima	98,8 %
Euroeficiencia	98,1 %
Datos Generales	
Sistema de refrigeración	Ventilación forzada
Caudal de aire	570 m ³ /h
Consumo en stand-by	20 W
Consumo nocturno	1 W
Temperatura de funcionamiento	-25 °C a 60 °C
Humedad relativa (sin condensación)	0 - 100 %
Grado de protección	IP65 / NEMA 4
Interruptor diferencial	1.000 mA
Altitud máxima ⁽⁴⁾	3.000 m
Conexión	AC: Máxima sección: 240 mm ² (un cable) Conexión DC: Máxima sección: 300 mm ² (un cable) Permitido el cableado en cobre y aluminio, tanto en DC como en AC
Marcado	CE
Normativa EMC y de seguridad	EN 61000-6-1, EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-3, EN 61000-6-4, EN 61000-3-2, EN 61000-3-3, EN 61000-3-11, EN 61000-3-12, EN 62109-1, EN 62109-2, IEC62103, EN 50178, FCC Part 15, IEC60068-2-1:2007, IEC60068-2-2:20007, IEC60068-2-14:2009, IEC60068-2-30:2005, IEC62116, IEC61683 y EN50530
Normativa de conexión a red	DIN V VDE V 0126-1-1, Arrêté du 23 avril 2008, EN 50438, EN 50439, EN 50549, CEI 0-21, CEI 0-16 VDE-AR-N 4105:2011-08, G59/3, P.0.12.3, AS4777.2, AS62040.1.1, BDEW, IEC 62116, IEC 61727, UNE 206007-1, ABNT NBR 16149, ABNT NBR 16150, Brazilian Grid Code, South African Grid Code, Chilean Grid Code, DEWA 2.0, Jordanian Grid Code, Thailand MEA & PEA requirements

Notas: ⁽¹⁾ La tensión mínima de baterías (627 V) se ha calculado para $V_{batería} = 1,085$ p.u. y $\cos \phi = 1$. Si $V_{batería}$ es diferente a este valor, la tensión mínima de baterías debe calcularse como: $V_{batería} = 627 * V_{batería} / 1,085$ ⁽²⁾ El inversor no entra en funcionamiento hasta que $V_{dc} < 1.000$ V ⁽³⁾ Por cada °C de aumento, la potencia de salida se reducirá un 2,3 % ⁽⁴⁾ Por encima de 1.000 m, la temperatura máxima para entregar potencia nominal se reduce a razón de 5,5 °C por cada 1.000 m adicionales.

Rendimiento INGECON® SUN STORAGE 100TL $V_{dc} = 627$ V

Figure 21. Inverter – Sun characteristics.

Integration Approach:

The main goal during integration is to run a parallel communication based on the IEEE 2030.5 with the already current installation based on ModBus.

Objectives:

- Deploy LPC and NATS on a local server to offload processing from energy devices.
- Ensure minimal latency in data communication to meet the real-time demands of the energy management system.
- Monitor a set of measurements from the inverter/battery
- Apply the LPC testing procedures

Services and Standards:

Service Deployment:

- Local Server: Host LPC and NATS on a dedicated local server.

Communication Protocols:

- IEEE 2030.5: Standard for device communication and data transformation (JSON/XML).
- NATS: Reliable, low-latency messaging system.
- Modbus: Default protocol for legacy devices.

Standard Procedure for Integration:

- Test deployment in InescTec Lab to get familiar with deployment procedures before real world implementation
- Local Server Setup: Configure a local server within the LAN to host the LPC and NATS services.
- Device Connection: Connect energy devices to the local server via LAN for data exchange.
- Protocol Conversion: Implementation and parametrization of the LPC on the local server to convert device-specific data to IEEE 2030.5 standard.
- Data Publishing: Implementation of NATS connector in EMS for LPC and publishing the converted data to the NATS topic for consumption by the EMS.
- Apply the testing procedures – Based on the procedures developed in WP2 the LPC will be tested and the log files recorded
- Monitoring and Maintenance: Establish monitoring tools and maintenance schedules to ensure the local server and services are running optimally.

4.3.4 Platform-Level Software Architecture: Integration Mapping for the EMS

The final mapping architecture is represented below in Figure 22. The deployment of the LPC will be done in a local PC already hosting the dispatch software (LabView). The communication is presently based on Modbus, which will remain in place to ensure continuity of operation and preserve the existing interface with the SCADA system. The existing PC has internet connection and will host Docker, the NATS server and the LPC. The message mapping will be done in order to monitor a set of variables from the inverter which is dedicated to the Lithium battery. After conducting the testing procedures, the system will continue running

with both message exchange protocols, and the corresponding log files will be retrieved for successful proof of monitoring and deployment.

Figure 22. Architecture of legacy protocol converter deployment at CapWatt UC05.

4.3.5 Showcase of the Integration

As a showcase example of Log file of the results in the Capwatt facilities test is presented in Figure 23. To do so the steps for the integration showcase at CapWatt are as follows:

1. Lab Testing: INESCTEC conducted lab deployment to learn procedures, supporting CapWatt.
2. Deployment Meetings: Schedule meetings for CapWatt deployment.
3. Testing Procedures: Run WP2 tests to verify implementation.
4. Monitoring and Logging: Define time windows, collect LPC log files to validate monitoring and deployment success.

```

2024-12-12 16:31:43,057 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Transformed message: {
  "lastUpdateTime": 1734021103054,
  "EventStatus": {
    "Grid frequency": 5001,
    "Output active power": 0,
    "potentiallySuperseded": false
  },
  "interval": {
    "Input 1 current": 16
  }
} {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,057 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Publishing message to topic: capwatts {}
2024-12-12 16:31:43,058 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.nats.AbstractNatsRequestHandler -- Publishing message: {
  "lastUpdateTime": 1734021103054,
  "EventStatus": {
    "Grid frequency": 5001,
    "Output active power": 0,
    "potentiallySuperseded": false
  },
  "interval": {
    "Input 1 current": 16
  }
} to topic: capwatts {}
    
```

Figure 23. Log file example of the results in the Capwatt facilities test.

Validation of Messages for IEEE 2030.5 Schema Compliance

- **Option:** The validation of IEEE 2030-5: As a configuration parameter defined per transformation in the LPC configuration file.
- **Behaviour:** When true, LPC validates messages for IEEE 2030.5 compliance on startup, logging errors and suggesting corrections if non-compliant.
- **Default:** False if not specified.

Deployment

- **General Deployment**
 - LPC can be deployed as a JAR or Docker container, requiring the configuration file path (default: ./conf) as an argument or mounted volume.
- **Configuration of Logging**
 - Uses Log4j for logging, configured via a log4j.xml file per Log4j documentation. Logs include INFO level and above to console and app.log, DEBUG level and above to debug_app.log, and LPC-specific logs to lpc.log for troubleshooting. Logs are stored in the logs folder, mountable to the host in Docker.
- **Building and Running LPC Using JAR**
 - Build the JAR using Maven, then deploy via Java with JRE 17. Optionally specify a custom configuration folder or logging configuration file path.
- **Building and Running LPC Using Docker**
 - Build the JAR, then create a Docker image. Run the container, mounting the configuration folder and optionally a custom logging configuration file. Pre-built images are available on Docker Hub.
- **Running LPC with Pre-built JAR**
 - Requires JRE 17. Download the JAR from the official GitHub repository and run via Java, optionally specifying a custom configuration folder.
- **Running LPC with Pre-built Docker Image**
 - Requires Docker. Pull the image from Docker Hub and run, mounting the configuration folder to the container.
- **How to Start NATS Server in Docker**
 - Pull the NATS image from Docker Hub and run it, exposing necessary ports. Configure LPC and NATS containers to use the same network for connectivity.

4.4 E-mobility architecture for Italian platform (ENEL X)

4.4.1 Introduction to the partner platform

The demonstrations carried out in the Italian pilot [3.6], for UC9, involve the integration of DERs in the *IoT/EMS/Flex* based ICT platforms of ENELX. For simplicity following is showed the architecture of the DERs and Tool integration to the ICT Platform.

Figure 24. Architecture of the EnelX Pilot for UC09

The EV chargers and the two large batteries systems communicate via Modbus TCP/IP, while the communication with residential Battery works in IEEE 2030.5 protocol. Thus, in order to establish communication with the EMS, an MQTT broker in IoT platform will act as a communication gateway for the EMS, and the messages between DERs and EMS will be mapped to IEEE 2030.5, via the LPC over NATS.

4.4.2 Overview of the platforms structure with different devices

In this sub-section we list, DERs and devices used in the EMS and Flex Platform. For the demonstration, as shown briefly in Figure 25, in order to deploy IEEE 2030.5 transformation, with the LPC tool, the following devices will be used:

Fields Assets:

- Lab 3.1 (Residential) includes:
 - 3SUN PV Small 2X3,7kWp= 7,4 (9 kWp in Bifacial way)
 - Storage small: Pylontech (LI-Ion) 4X 4,8 kW
- Lab 3.2 (SMALL C&I) includes:
 - 3SUN PV: 2x12kWp= 24 kWp (29kWp in bifacial way)
 - Greentech Storage: 1X5,5kW super capacitor energy intensive
- Lab 5 (Large C&I) includes:
 - 3SUN PV: 102kWp (125kWp in Bifacial way)
 - LG Storage large assembled by SOCOMEC 132 kVA- 274kWh Lithium Battery
- LAB 9:
 - 2 V2G residential EV charger CHAdeMO +/-15kW

XLAB Control Room:

- High performance server with:
 - LPC
 - NATS
 - IEEE 2030.5 server
 - Router with MVNO Sim to connect data flow to IT platforms
- IT platforms
 - IoT Platform
 - EMS platform
 - Flex Platform

Figure 25. Networking of Field Assets in EnelX Lab and IT platform

4.4.3 Approach used for software tool integration

The approach used to develop the Middleware environment in order to connect the Field Assets with the Application/Service platform is based on the fact that in the Italian Pilot two protocols have been implemented IEEE 2030.5 Schneider natively protocol on XW pro inverter product and Modbus protocol on Utility scale battery (Socomec by LG) and Mobility EV V2G chargers. Following the description of the task implemented.

Selected Option for the deployment of this pilot is similar to option 3.3: Local Server to Deploy Software Tools. Among the alternatives based on more local implementations (on the device side, platform side or dedicated local server), the local sever approach occurred as the most suitable one for three reasons:

- First, deploying software in a local server brings a significant level of flexibility by decoupling the integration level from the legacy systems' limitations. The engineers can work in a significantly less “regulated” environment at the integration stage.
- Second, the presence of IEEE 2030.3 native endpoint in the Italian pilot required both one flow to manage IEEE 2030.5 client and another flow to manage Modbus register and the cascaded conversion stages as depicted in Figure 24.
- Third the choice of local server option facilitated the integration with EnelX IoT platform and MQTT broker for telemetries and for command flows in order to respect Third Party integration specifications dictated by IoT platform.

Integration Approach:

The main goal of integration for this pilot is to monitor and control multi-physics HESS comprising batteries, EV chargers through a local EMS platform and implement between end-points (EMS platform by means of IoT platform and DERs) a communication based on IEEE 2030.5.

- Objectives:
 - Deploy LPC and NATS on a local server in XLAB

- Monitor power injection of the PV, power consumption of the load, state-of-charge of the battery and EV's V2G parameters
- Send control set-points to controllable DERs to optimize the behaviour of multi-physics HESS in a different topology (use cases)
- Harmonize DER-EMS/IoT communication under presence of different communication paradigms (client-server)

Figure 26. Integration approach selected for Italian Pilot

Services and Standards:

- Service Deployment:
 - Local Server based in XLAB Control Room: Deploy LPC and NATS on a dedicated device (Dedicated server).
- Communication Protocols:
 - IEEE 2030.5: Standard for device communication and data transformation.
 - NATS: Messaging system to ensure reliable and low-latency data transfer
 - Modbus is the default existing communication protocol of the DERs (EVs included).

Standard Procedure for Integration:

- Test deployment of software in the Xlab server, DERs setting and mapping in the hardware network topology, to list all the variables used and registers needed.
- Local Server Setup: Configure a local server within the LAN with docker engine to host the LPC and NATS services.
- Device Connection: Connect DERs to the local server with IP addressing mapping via LAN for data exchange and configure the router and SIM MVNO to address the AWS IT servers (IoT and EMS) and virtual firewall for configuration of routes and services allowed
- Protocol Conversion: Implementation and parametrization of the LPC on the local server to convert device-specific data to IEEE 2030.5 standard.
- Data Publishing: Implementation of NATS connector in the EMS for LPC and publishing the converted data to the NATS topic for consumption by the EMS.

- Apply the testing procedures – Based on the procedures developed in WP2 the LPC will be tested and the log files recorded in EMS
- Monitoring and Maintenance: Establish monitoring tools and maintenance schedules to ensure the local server and services are running optimally.

4.4.4 Platform-Level Software Architecture: Integration Mapping for the EMS

To implement the Middleware integration the Interoperability software was exploited to connect two endpoints supporting both protocols IEEE 2030.5 and Modbus protocol. Therefore, an architecture that consists in LPC instances mapping Modbus devices to cover asset with Modbus protocol conversion to MQTT protocol to cover asset with Modbus protocol conversion and LPC instances mapping IEEE 2030.5 to MQTT integration with the communication endpoints.

Figure 27. Integration Mapping for Application and Services integration

- 1) LPC gateway: Installation and configuration
 - LPC Installation: <https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Legacy-Protocol-Converter>
 - NATS server installation
 - LPC configuration: the Yaml File has been set for each asset through Sunesis UI at <https://sunesis.si/interstore/lpc/transformations> address.
 - YAML Files for single asset connected have been set : an example is showed in the following figure
 - The integration of LPC with ENX IoT platform has required the implementation of additional development following the IoT Specs “Third party Integration specifications”(In Sunesis SW LPC version 1.3.0) to integrate the flows coming from assets and going to the asset: registration of the LPC gateway in IoT platform has required generation and management of Infocert certificate
 - LPC has required (Sunesis SW version 1.3.2), in addition, to implement AWS shadows commands in order to manage power set point commands coming from EMS platform to the assets on field.

Figure 28. Integration of LPC gateway

2) IEEE 2030.5 Preparation activities:

- Installation IEEE 2030.5 Server downloaded from https://github.com/quantumscript/IEEE_2030_5_gridapspd_server and integrated in WP3-D3.4: provide the entire stack of IEEE 2030.5 server;
- Installation Client Server IEEE NATS library: <https://github.com/INESCTEC/InterSTORE---Client-Server>: Provide an open source, out-of-the-box support for IEEE 2030.5 communication between devices and IT systems (IoT and EMS);
- CA Certification installation on server side released by Certificate Authority (CA); the client certification has been prebuilt and released by Schneider vendor.
- *Native IEEE 2030.5 Client* Schneider provided by Schneider supply: Schneider XWPro Conext Gateway product model 865-0330 natively IEEE 2030.5 (in the figure 29 the IEEE 2030.5 CSIP Sunspec certification for the Conext Gateway Schneider product installed in Italian LAB).

Figure 29. Sunspec Alliance Certificate for XWpro Gateway

3) Integration tests:

Client = DER Device Conext Gateway XWPRO (Schneider)

Server = CSIP-compliant server

Following in the *Figure 30* the block diagram of the IEEE 2030.5 Client-Server integration:

Figure 30. Integration of IEEE 2030.5 Client-Server

- Here's a breakdown of the handshake and integration process between a DER client and a server in IEEE 2030.5
- In IEEE 2030.5 Client initiates all communication in client-pull model
- The first step is the TLS version 1.2 handshake using HTTPS over TCP
 - Mutual certificate-based authentication
 - The server presents its certificate (X.509) to the client.
 - The client-DER resource presents its own certificate, pre-installed by the vendor provisioned via secure onboarding
 - Certificates are signed by a trusted Certificate Authority (CA) – defined by jurisdictional standards (e.g., California Rule 21 / CSIP uses CA-signed certs)
- A secure, encrypted channel is established, and identities are authenticated.

In Figure 31 the UI of Schneider XWpro Conext Gateway-Client with the information from Server IP address and Port and the SLFDI (Server Long Form Device Identifier) calculate by the Server, LFDI (Client Long Form Device Identifier) and SFDI (Client Short Form Device Identifier) supplied by Schneider.

The green light appears in the Client UI to indicate that the Server connection is established and the handshake session has ended successfully. From this session starts the exchange data as foreseen in the IEEE 2030.5 Protocol literature/rules (cfr .SunSpec Common Smart Inverter Profile (CSIP) Conformance Test Procedures).

Following are reported part of the logs from the Initial process of integration: secure key exchange and handshake process success.

```
iee2030-server | [1761057809] Connection from 10.40.160.174:443
iee2030-server | [1761057812] Connection from 10.40.160.174:443
iee2030-server | SSL handshake successful with 10.40.160.174
iee2030-server | [10.40.160.174] Request: /dcap
java-backend | 2025-10-21T14:43:22.363Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-7] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet : GET "/dcap", parameters={}, headers={masked} in DispatcherServlet 'dispatcherServlet'
java-backend | 2025-10-21T14:43:22.363Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-7] s.w.s.m.m.a.RequestMappingHandlerMapping : Mapped to interstore.DeviceCapability.DcapManager#getDeviceCapability(HttpServletRequest, HttpServletResponse)
java-backend | 2025-10-21T14:43:22.364Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-7] o.s.web.method.HandlerMethod : Arguments: [org.apache.catalina.connector.RequestFacade@2bf9a4f4, org.apache.catalina.connector.ResponseFacade@253e4ffb]
java-backend | 2025-10-21T14:43:22.367Z INFO 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-7] i.DeviceCapability.DcapManager : Server certificate processed - LFDI: faba4524ff2d734befaad8320384c41b049be845, SFDI: 673041823510
```

```

java-backend | 2025-10-21T14:43:22.372Z INFO 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-7] i.DeviceCapability.DcapManager :
the dcap_val is <DeviceCapability xsi:schemaLocation="urn:ieee:std:2030.5:ns sep.xsd"
xmlns="urn:ieee:std:2030.5:ns" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" href="/dcap">
java-backend | <TimeLink href="/dcap/tm"/>
java-backend | <EndDeviceListLink all="1" href="/edev"/>
java-backend | </DeviceCapability>
java-backend | 2025-10-21T14:43:22.374Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-7] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet :
No view rendering, null ModelAndView returned.
java-backend | 2025-10-21T14:43:22.374Z DEBUG 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-7] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet :
Completed 200 OK, headers={masked}
ieee2030-server | Response: HTTP/1.1 200 OK
ieee2030-server | Content-Type: application/sep+xml
ieee2030-server | Content-Length: 262
ieee2030-server | X-Server-LFDI: faba4524ff2d734bfaad8320384c41b049be845
ieee2030-server | X-Server-SFDI: 673041823510
    
```

Figure 31. Test Logs of handshake process,secure keys exchange to establish Client-Server secure connection

IEEE 2030.5

Remote control

Local control

IP Address

10.40.160.184

Port

443

Connection status ●

Last transfer time

--:--:--

Server Long Form Device Identifier(SLFDI)

faba4524ff2d734bfaad8320384c41b049be845

Server DCAP path

/dcap

Client Long Form Device Identifier(LFDI)

c63fb011cd6be6951d36b85a6261566d316af3c2

Client Short Form Device Identifier(SFDI)

532170017563

Figure 32. IEEE 2030.5 Schneider inverter XWpro client setting

The details of the testing procedure tool for the evidence of the IEEE 2030.5 Client-Server integration results will be reported in D3.4 with the logs of tests and validation in laboratory environment with the tool developed in WP2.3 InterSTORE project.

4.4.5 Showcase of the Integration

This section demonstrates the integration of the LPC with the EMS/IoT platform in the Italian pilot by elaborating:

(1) configuration and implementation of the LPC YAML formatted (connections and transformation) configuration files for different flows:

a) configuration on EMS of assets and load area of DERs, telemetries flow acquisition from field assets;

b) running algorithm and disaggregated commands flow are sent to the assets.

(2) validation of the LPC configurations through the log files generated by the LPC and comparing the telemetries read in LPC with Scada value read directly on the meters during the operation

(3) verification on IT platform (EMS/IoT) that the a) assets' telemetries are correctly received by EMS through IoT platform and the flex order is correctly disaggregated on the assets of DERs and b) command power setpoint are correctly implemented on the single target asset.

The first step of the LPC configuration is the definition of the input/output connections of the LPC using the Sunesis SW mask at <https://sunesis.si/interstore/lpc/connections>.

In the following pictures are reported examples of LPC mapping of Modbus utility scale battery (Socomec) for telemetry flow and command shadow (power setpoint) flow.

Example : MODBUS-IEEE2030.5 variables reading «SOC» SOCOMEC

Figure 33. Test of configuration input/output connections of the LPC for telemetry flow and command flow

In the second step the verification that the telemetries values read and transformed are correct comparing with the SCADA value read directly on the assets.

```

version: 1.0.0
connections:
  - name: Com_BATS
    type: BATS
    host: nats://localhost
    port: 4222
  - name: Com_SOCOEC
    type: Modbus
    host: 19.48.160.174
    port: 502
transformations:
  - name: ESS_Pylontech_KLab3_HB_BATS
    connections:
      incoming-connection:
        - Com_SOCOEC
      outgoing-connection:
        - Com_BATS
    outgoing-format: 350H
    to-outgoing:
      to-nats: event/send
      message: |
        {
          "device_type": "nats-client",
          "thing_id": "Storage_Lab3",
          "tags": [
            {
              "name": "SOC",
              "timestamp": 1733331872324,
              "trendId": "1234567",
              "value": {
                "DER": [
                  {
                    "description": "SOC Pylontech",
                    "StateOfChargeStatusType": {
                      "value": 17
                    }
                  }
                ]
              }
            }
          ]
        }
    interval-request:
      interval: 3000
    request:
      modbus-function-code: 3
      modbus-device-id: 238
      modbus-registers:
        register-address: 40001
        type: int16
    timestamp: 2024-09-24T12:51:55.666Z
  
```

Example :MODBUS –IEEE2030.5 –READING «SOC» PYLONTEC LAB3

```

"device_type": "nats-client",
"thing_id": "Storage_Lab3",
"data": {
  "tags": [
    {
      "name": "SOC",
      "timestamp": 1733331872324,
      "trendId": "1234567",
      "value": {
        "DER": [
          {
            "description": "SOC Pylontech",
            "StateOfChargeStatusType": {
              "value": 17
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  ]
}
  
```

Scada value

BATTERY 1 - LAB. 3.1	
INFO BATTERIA	
STATO CARICA	17 %

Figure 34. Verification that the value reported in the Yaml implementation corresponds to value red on Scada system

The third step reported is the operation of the EMS/IOT System integration: the verification on IT platform (EMS/IOT) that the a) assets' telemetries are correctly received by EMS through IoT platform and b) command setpoint are correctly implemented on the target asset.

Figure 35. Registration outcome on Device Management Console of IoT platform

Figure 36. Infocert registration of LPC gateway in IoT platform

```
5/16/25, 4:07 PMSunesis6_thing1 > esol_ap3562902_qa/sunesis6/ieee2030/sunesis6_thing1/data
Raw Message:
{"device_type":"mqtt-client","thing_id":"sunesis6_thing1","data":{"tags":[{"name":"Pylontech SOC","timestamp":1747404435993,"trendId":"13000000","value":31},{"name":"Pylontech P active","timestamp":1747404435993,"trendId":"86900000","value":-299}]}}
Parsed Message:
device_type: "mqtt-client"
thing_id: "sunesis6_thing1"
data:
tags:
0:
name: "Pylontech SOC"
timestamp: 1747404435993
trendId: "13000000"
value: 31
1:
name: "Pylontech P active"
timestamp: 1747404435993
```

Figure 37. Telemetries flow received in IoT platform

Figure 38. Telemetries flow received in EMS platform

Once the load area has been configured and the algorithm is started for the calculation of single quote of the aggregated DER (load area) the power set point is sent to the Load Area configured and a result notification is received in EMS platform.

Figure 39. EMS load areas configured and flex order is applied

To conclude we can summarize that the Italian Pilot, held in EnelX Lab in Rome, has successfully demonstrated that network flexibility services are implemented in real life through InterSTORE tools' development and integration implementation with IT platforms: here's a structured mapping of software/middleware tools & protocols, and standards, that help enable interoperability between Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) and Energy Management Systems (EMS), particularly in contexts where there are legacy or proprietary protocols. The goal is to overcome mismatches, ensure modern standard compliance, and allow EMS platforms to communicate cleanly with diverse DERs.

4.5 Energy management architectures in Germany (FZJ, EATON)

In this sub-section different suggested activities can be classified as follows:

4.5.1 Introduction to the partner platform

The demonstrations carried out in the German pilot [3.7], for UC3 and UC8, involve the integration of distributed energy resources (DERs) in the FIWARE-based ICT platform of FZJ, for UC3, and in the EMS platform of EATON, in UC8. For simplicity, since the architectures of the two use cases are almost identical, in the following we will refer to the one of UC8. The two battery systems (Riello, with high power, and Tesla, with high energy) and the large photovoltaic (PV) system communicate via Modbus TCP/IP, while the communication with the heat pump (HP) communicates via MQTT. Thus, in order to establish communication with the EMS, an MQTT broker will act as a communication gateway for the EMS, and the messages between DERs and EMS will be mapped to IEEE 2030.5, via the LPC over NATS.

The computation hardware of the EMS platform deployed, SMP 4250, in the pilot belongs to Eaton's grid automation solutions product line [3.8]. It was designed to help the distribution utilities to expand their monitoring capabilities. The internal architecture of the SMP 4250 consists of a series of software components known as protocol components as depicted in Figure 40. Slave protocol components handle the necessary functions to process requests from a SCADA system or a back-end platform, while master protocol components manage the functions required to poll devices and send control requests to intelligent electronic devices (IED). It supports several standard communication protocols such as IEC 61850, DNP3, Modbus, IEC 60870-5-101/104 in smart grid ecosystem as well as numerous proprietary protocols like SEL, ABB TEN BYTE, and Motorola MDAC. Besides these protocols, the REST API interface of the platform provides programmatic access to the SMP Device, which can be used to manage and/or obtain information about the SMP Device through different services. The master protocol component polls devices and stores the retrieved data in an internal database called Real-Time Data Exchange (RTDX).

Figure 40. Eaton SMP 4250 internals: master and slave protocols and real-time data exchange.

RTDX holds the current values of all device data points, along with additional information provided by substation devices, such as data quality and timestamps. It also stores information like device tags used for control functions [3.9]Error! Reference source not found.. Besides offering connectivity functions, SMP 4250 features software-based programmable

logic controllers (Soft PLC) that can automate management of field devices. In practice, a control logic deployed in the platform interact with RTDX in the runtime, using data originated from either slave or master side of the communication.

For the pilot activities, the control logic was intended to control the DERs in multi-physics HESS in UC8 –specifically electrical heat pump and batteries. The control logic was developed in CODESYS environment [3.10].

It is important to note that, with its large portfolio of master and slave protocols, SMP 4250 serves as a protocol converter in many grid monitoring applications, and thus, closes the gap between the DSO control room and the propriety IED used in grid monitoring. However, this platform does not natively support IEEE 2030.5. Therefore, to deploy SMP 4250 as an energy management platform within the InterSTORE interoperability concept, one must integrate the interoperability tools such as LPC to the platform. The following subsections elaborate on how the LPC was integrated to SMP 4250.

4.5.2 Overview of the platforms structure with different devices

For the demonstration, in order to deploy IEEE 2030.5 with the LPC, the following devices will be used:

- Riello battery system (DER, 1500 kW/500 kWh, Native communication based on Modbus TCP/IP)
- Tesla battery system (DER, 500 kW/2.5 MWh, Native communication based on Modbus TCP/IP)
- Photovoltaic system (DER, 1.1MWp, Native communication based on Modbus TCP/IP)
- Heat pump (DER, avg. 200 kW, Native communication based on MQTT)
- Raspberry Pi 4b (RPi), to deploy the LPC and the NATS server in docker containers.
- MQTT broker
- EATON SMP 4250 (EMS)

The IEEE 2030.5 standard facilitates structured messaging formats, promoting interoperability and consistent data representation across various devices and platforms. However, during this study, no DERs at the FZJ campus supported the IEEE 2030.5 protocol natively. Additionally, the Eaton EMS hardware used for real-time control and monitoring off HESS was incompatible with IEEE 2030.5. Nevertheless, the LPC, allows for transformation between legacy protocols and IEEE 2030.5. Even when none of the communication ends (i.e., DERs in HESS and EMS platform) natively support IEEE 2030.5, there exist practical solutions to establish a structured communication using data models of this protocol. One such solution is cascading two instances of LPCs in the communication chain as presented in Figure 41.

Figure 41. Cascaded deployment of LPCs to enable IEEE 2030.5 communication with non-native endpoints.

4.5.3 Approach used for software tool integration

Considering the presence of DERs and EMS in the same physical environment and the ability to leverage a local communication network to connect two ends –namely the DERs and EMS platform in the pilot, the architecture option 3.2 Aggregator NATS from chapter 3, was not a resource efficient approach. Among the alternatives based on more local implementations (on the device side, platform side or dedicated local server), the local sever approach, approach 3.3. on chapter 3, occurred as the most suitable one for two (one general and one German pilot specific) reasons. First, deploying software in a local server, as elaborated in section 4.2.3 for Spanish pilot, brings a significant level of flexibility by decoupling the integration level from the legacy systems' limitations. The engineers can work in a significantly less “regulated” environment at the integration stage. Second, the lack of IEEE 2030.5 native endpoint in the German pilot required cascaded conversion stages as depicted in Figure 41. The choice of local server option facilitated the integration thanks to the ability to “re-use” the integration experience in DER side gained in Task 3.2 (as formally reported in Deliverable 3.2 Software Tool Integration to Selected Devices in German pilot) in the other end of the communication, for Integration to Platforms.

Integration Approach:

Goals and Objectives:

Goal: To monitor and control multi-physics HESS comprising batteries and electrical heat pumps through a local EMS platform and implement between endpoints (EMS platform and DERs) a communication based on IEEE 2030.5

Objectives:

- Deploy LPC and NATS on a local device (RPi).
- Monitor power injection of the PV, power consumption of the load, state-of-charge of the battery and temperature of the thermal energy storage system connected to heat pump.
- Send control set-points to controllable DERs (HP and batteries) to optimize the behaviour of multi-physics HESS
- Harmonize DER-EMS communication under presence of different communication of paradigms (client-server)

Services and Standards:

Service Deployment:

- Local Server: Deploy LPC and NATS on a dedicated device (RPi).

Communication Protocols:

- IEEE 2030.5: Standard for device communication and data transformation.
- NATS: Messaging system to ensure reliable and low-latency data transfer
- Modbus and MQTT are the default existing communication protocols of the DERs.

Standard Procedure for Integration (incremental prototyping approach):

1. Test deployment of software in the loop in the EATON lab, and in the hardware in the loop (HiL lab) at FZJ, to get familiar with deployment procedures before real-world implementation
2. Local Server Setup: Configure a local server within the LAN to host the LPC and NATS services.
3. Device Connection: Connect DERs to the local server via LAN for data exchange.
4. Protocol Conversion: Implementation and parametrization of the LPC on the local server to convert device-specific data to IEEE 2030.5 standard.
5. Data Publishing: Implementation of NATS connector in the EMS for LPC and publishing the converted data to the NATS topic for consumption by the EMS.
6. Apply the testing procedures – Based on the procedures developed in WP2 the LPC will be tested and the log files recorded
7. Monitoring and Maintenance: Establish monitoring tools and maintenance schedules to ensure the local server and services are running optimally.

4.5.4 Platform-Level Software Architecture: Integration Mapping for the EMS

As mentioned in sub-section 4.5.4, the interoperability software was exploited to close the gap between two endpoints that do not support IEEE 2030.5 protocol. Therefore, an architecture that consists of cascaded deployment of two LPC instances, one for EMS platform and one for HESS was followed in the German pilot. Figure 42 depicts each protocol conversion instance alongside with the communication endpoints. The integration of interoperability software in devices –the lower part of Figure 41– will be elaborated in *Deliverable 3.2 – Report on the Software Integration to Selected Devices* [3.4]. This sub-section details the integration mapping of the software tool within the Eaton EMS platform.

Figure 42. Eaton EMS platform's integration to multi-physics hybrid energy storage system in FZJ campus.

As can be seen in Figure z, the Eaton EMS platform has three software components:

- **Multi-physics EMS algorithm:** This component directly runs on the SMP 4250 hardware. It is programmed using Codesys Workbench. It is a rule base algorithm that creates new set points to the controllable DERs in the HESS –namely the batteries and HP- upon reading their instantaneous states. The interested readers are advised to view the project deliverable *D4.1 - New generation EMS for HEMS, HESS and flexibility management report* [3.11] to access detailed description of the decision logic.
- **Synchronization Container:** This component is essentially a Docker container, written in Python, running on a Raspberry Pi integrated into the SMP 4250 hardware over its REST API. This software ensures synchronized measurements for the energy management algorithm operating on the SMP 4250. The need for this software arises from the fact that data from most monitored DERs (load, PV, batteries) are read by the LPC-DER from corresponding Modbus registers at predefined intervals, synchronized with the LPC's clock. Conversely, for the LPC-DER to access data from the HP, it subscribes to a specific topic and waits for the HP MQTT agent to send the data. Crucially, this constitutes a system where multiple communication instances are triggered by

different clock references. To prevent the energy management platform from executing the algorithm with non-synchronized measurement data, which would lead to poor decisions in assigning new set points to the controllable DERs in the HESS, a synchronization stage is required. This synchronization is achieved by integrating the "Synchronization Container" into the platform. Practically, this software receives MQTT messages (transformed by LPC-EMS under specific topics), checks if sufficient data has been received (i.e., if all DERs have sent their instantaneous measurements) at each control interval (e.g., 1 minutes), and if this condition is met, it *POSTs* the state of the HESS as a whole—with data from all DERs—to the EMS algorithm. Likewise, it *GETs* the newly generated set points by the algorithm and *publishes* them back to the LPC-EMS, which will perform the necessary transformation.

- *LPC-EMS*: This component, a Docker container running on the Raspberry Pi, ensures that the measurement data sent to EMS platform over NATS network using IEEE 2030.5 models are transformed to format that can be easily read by the EMS platform. Likewise, it performs necessary transformations from the EMS side into the IEEE 2030.5 data models to inform the DERs in the HESS about the new set points. The LPC deployed in the EMS platform instance has several transformation, each detailed in the following table:

Table 2: List of transformation in LPC in EMS platform in German Pilot.

Description	From	To
Read HP measurements	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/hp/status IEEE 2030.5 model: mirror-MeterReadingList	Connection: MQTT-EMS (EMS platform) Topic: ems/hp/status IEEE 2030.5 model: --
Read battery measurements	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/bat/status IEEE 2030.5 model: DERStatus	Connection: MQTT-EMS (EMS platform) Topic: ems/bat/status IEEE 2030.5 model: --
Read PV measurements	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/pv/status IEEE 2030.5 model: mirror-MeterReadingList	Connection: MQTT-EMS (EMS platform) Topic: ems/pv/status IEEE 2030.5 model: --
Read load measurements	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/load/status IEEE 2030.5 model: mirror-MeterReadingList	Connection: MQTT-EMSr (EMS platform) Topic: ems/load/status IEEE 2030.5 model: --
Publish set-points to HP	Connection: MQTT-EMS (EMS platform) Topic: ems/setpoints/building IEEE 2030.5 model: --	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/setpoints/heatpump IEEE 2030.5 model: derControl
Publish set-points to battery	Connection: MQTT-EMS (EMS platform) Topic: ems/setpoints/building IEEE 2030.5 model: --	Connection: NATS-Server Topic: nats/setpoints/battery IEEE 2030.5 model: derControl

4.5.5 Showcase of the Integration

This section demonstrates the integration of the LPC with the EMS platform in the German pilot by elaborating (1) configuration of the LPC through the YAML formatted configuration files, and (2) validation of the LPC configurations through the log files generated by the LPC during the operations.

The first step of the LPC configuration is the definition of the input/output connections of the LPC. The configuration file presented in Figure 43 shows that the LPC connected to the Eaton EMS in the German pilot transforms between end points NATS-Server and MQTT-EMS. The former represents the DER side of the deployment and carries exclusively IEEE 2030.5 formatted messages. The latter represents the connection to the EMS platform and is in essence an MQTT broker that is hosted by the RPi. The IP host and port numbers of the pilot are censored for the sake of security.

```
connections:
- name: NATS-Server
  type: NATS
  host: [REDACTED]
  port: [REDACTED]
  reconnect: true
- name: MQTT-EMS
  type: MQTT
  version: 3
  host: [REDACTED]
  port: [REDACTED]
```

Figure 43. LPC configuration for Eaton EMS - connections

The second step of the LPC configuration is the definition of the transformations. As elaborated in Table 2, the LPC instance is capable of 6 transformations. The first four rows are about monitoring the DERs and the last two are about control of them. The following screenshots present the details of one of the monitoring and control transformations implemented in the pilot.

Figure 44 shows that the LPC is programmed to read the battery status under the NATS topic *nats/bat/status* and publishes an MQTT message under the MQTT topic *ems/bat/status*. This message is transferred to the synchronization container (see Figure 42) through the MQTT broker. As can be seen in the screenshot, the published message is a JSON message where the "stateOfChargeStatus" is mapped from the "*DERStatus/stateOfChargeStatus/value/value*" of the incoming message. The LPC receives this IEEE 2030.5 formatted message from the NATS network.

An example instance of this transformation is given in Figure 45. In this example, the LPC logs the information "Incoming message on topic *nats/bat/status* from device:" and the received message indicating the *DERStatus*. The log file indicates that a JSON message is created where the *DERStatus.readingTime* is mapped to *Bat1Status.readingTime* and *DERStatus.stateOfChargeStatus.value.value* is mapped to *Bat1Status.stateOfChargeStatus.value*. This shows that the incoming message is IEEE 2030.5 formatted while the outgoing message is configured according to the requirements of the EMS.

```

- name: EMS reads Bat status
description: LPC converts NATS message (in JSON form) containing DER (Bat1) status to MQTT (in JSON form)
validate-ieee2030-5: false
connections:
  incoming-connection:
    - NATS-Server
  incoming-topic: nats/bat/status
  incoming-format: JSON
  outgoing-connection:
    - MQTT-EMS
  outgoing-topic: ems/bat/status
  outgoing-format: JSON
to-outgoing:
  to-topic: ems/bat/status
  message: |-
    {
      "Bat1Status": {
        "readingTime": {
          "lpc:mapping": {
            "path": "DERStatus/readingTime",
            "type": "datetime",
            "pattern": "dd-MM-yyyy HH:mm:ss"
          }
        },
        "stateOfChargeStatus": {
          "dateTime": {
            "lpc:mapping": {
              "path": "DERStatus/stateOfChargeStatus/dateTime",
              "type": "datetime",
              "pattern": "dd-MM-yyyy HH:mm:ss"
            }
          },
          "value": {
            "lpc:mapping": {
              "path": "DERStatus/stateOfChargeStatus/value/value",
              "type": "integer"
            }
          }
        }
      }
    }
  
```

Figure 44. LPC configuraton for Eaton EMS – transformation for monitoring

```

2025-03-04 14:59:43,833 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Incoming message on topic nats/bat/status from device:
{
  "DERStatus": {
    "readingTime": 1741096783522,
    "stateOfChargeStatus": {
      "dateTime": 1741096783522,
      "value": {
        "value": 100
      }
    }
  }
}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,879 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Value at JSON path /DERStatus/readingTime : 1741096783522 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,880 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Pattern: dd-MM-yyyy HH:mm:ss {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,880 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Date value to parse: 1741096783522 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,882 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: /DERStatus/readingTime, value: "04-03-2025 14:59:43" {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,888 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Value at JSON path /DERStatus/stateOfChargeStatus/dateTime : 1741096783522 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,888 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Pattern: dd-MM-yyyy HH:mm:ss {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,888 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Date value to parse: 1741096783522 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,889 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: /DERStatus/stateOfChargeStatus/dateTime, value: "04-03-2025 14:59:43" {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,895 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Value at JSON path /DERStatus/stateOfChargeStatus/value/value : 100 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:43,896 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: /DERStatus/stateOfChargeStatus/value/value, value: 100 {}
2025-03-04 14:59:44,017 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Transformed message:
{
  "Bat1Status": {
    "readingTime": "04-03-2025 14:59:43",
    "stateOfChargeStatus": {
      "dateTime": "04-03-2025 14:59:43",
      "value": 100
    }
  }
}
  
```

Figure 45. LPC transformation in Eaton EMS – logging a monitoring instance

Figure 46 shows that the LPC is programmed to receive the battery set point from the EMS (over the MQTT broker) as an XML file under the MQTT topic *ems/setpoints/building1* and publish a JSON message under the NATS topic *nats/setpoints/battery* to inform the battery about the new set points. Here, the outgoing message follows the requirements of IEEE

2030.5. Therefore, the LPC maps the corresponding values (i.e. EMSCommand/battery) to the `derControl.derControlBase.opModFixedW.value` entry.

```

- name: EMS publishes set points for battery
  description: LPC-EMS routes MQTT message containing set points to storage devices
  connections:
    incoming-connection:
      - MQTT-EMS
    incoming-topic: ems/setpoints/building1
    incoming-format: XML
    outgoing-connection:
      - NATS-Server
    outgoing-topic: nats/setpoints/battery
    outgoing-format: JSON
  to-outgoing:
    to-topic: nats/setpoints/battery
    message: |-
      {
        "derControl": {
          "derControlBase": {
            "opModFixedW": {
              "value": {
                "lpc:mapping": {
                  "path": "/EMSCommand/battery",
                  "type": "float32"
                }
              }
            }
          }
        }
      },

```

Figure 46. LPC configuration for Eaton EMS – transformation for control

An example instance of the transformation defined in Figure 46 is shown in Figure 47 and Figure 48. The first one shows the logs for the incoming message. As can be seen, the incoming message indicates the set points to the battery and heat pump in a single XML message. The LPC maps these values to two separate messages. One of them, depicted in Figure 48, is targeted to the battery. At this stage, the LPC creates a `DERControl` message and publishes it to the topic `nats/setpoints/battery` in the network.

```

2025-03-04 15:08:06,301 INFO -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Incoming message on topic ems/setpoints/building1 from device:
<EMSCommand>
  <datetime>04-03-2025 15:08:04</datetime>
  <battery>11.454544</battery>
  <heatpump>0.0</heatpump>
</EMSCommand>
{}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,683 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Value at XML path /EMSCommand/battery : 11.454544 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,684 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: /EMSCommand/battery, value: 11.454544 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,687 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Value at XML path /EMSCommand/heatpump : 0.0 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,689 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: /EMSCommand/heatpump, value: 0.0 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,690 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Value at XML path /EMSCommand/datetime : 04-03-2025 15:08:04 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,690 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Pattern: dd-MM-yyyy HH:mm:ss {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,690 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Date value to parse: 04-03-2025 15:08:04 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,701 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Value at XML path /EMSCommand/datetime : 04-03-2025 15:08:04 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,702 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Pattern: dd-MM-yyyy HH:mm:ss {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,702 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Date value to parse: 04-03-2025 15:08:04 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,759 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Parsed date: Tue Mar 04 15:08:04 CET 2025 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,764 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.mappers.AbstractMapper -- Parsed date: Tue Mar 04 15:08:04 CET 2025 {}
2025-03-04 15:08:06,767 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.ObjectTransformer -- path: /EMSCommand/datetime, value: "1741097284000" {}

```

Figure 47. LPC transformation in Eaton EMS - logging a control instance (incoming))

```

2025-03-04 15:08:06,773 DEBUG -- si.sunesis.interoperability.lpc.transformations.transformation.TransformationHandler -- Publishing message to topic: nats/setpoints/battery with message: {
  "derControl": {
    "derControlBase": {
      "opModFixedW": {
        "value": 11.454544
      }
    },
    "creationTime": 1741097286302,
    "eventStatus": {
      "currentStatus": 1,
      "dateTime": "1741097284000",
      "potentiallySuperseded": false
    },
    "interval": {
      "start": 10
    },
    "mId": {
      "value": [
        110.0,
        117.0,
        98.0,
        105.0,
        98.0,
        117.0,
        115.0
      ]
    }
  }
}
}()

```

Figure 48. LPC transformation in Eaton EMS - logging a control instance (outgoing)

It is important to note that the incoming messages related to monitoring function comply with the IEEE 2030.5 data format while the outgoing messages can be formatted more flexibly as the EMS system does not natively support IEEE 2030.5. For the same reason, the incoming messages from the EMS side (MQTT-EMS) to the LPC are not formatted according to IEEE 2030.5 whereas the outgoing messages are IEEE 2030.5.

5 CONCLUSION

The platform-level integrations carried out within the InterSTORE project demonstrate the flexibility, adaptability, and robustness of the interoperability tools developed in WP2. Across the different platforms of project partners in this report—CyberGrid in Austria, HESStec with HyDEMS in Spain, INESC TEC/CapWATT in Portugal, ENELX for the Italian E-mobility pilot, and the German platform at FZJ/EATON—each deployment with architecture mapping has been tailored to local technical conditions, operational needs, and specific use cases, while adhering to the common objective of enabling seamless, standardised communication between heterogeneous energy assets and EMS platforms.

CyberGrid's integration showcased the direct incorporation of the IEEE 2030.5 client/server library into the CyberNoc flexibility management platform, enabling real-time aggregation of diverse DERs in a community setting. HESStec's implementation in the GridLab leveraged a local server deployment (Option 3) with single LPC to combine ultra-fast local control with the capability to interface with external aggregators which can provide high power services such as frequency control, virtual inertia and fast peak shaving. The INESC TEC/CapWATT deployment in Portugal applied the same local server approach, maintaining parallel Modbus and IEEE 2030.5 communications to ensure continuity of existing operations while enabling new interoperability functions.

ENELX's e-mobility platform illustrated the use of the local server model to harmonise communication between multi-physics hybrid energy systems—spanning large-scale batteries, PV generation, and V2G chargers—and the EMS/IoT platforms, meeting both technical and regulatory integration requirements. Finally, the German platform demonstrated the dual LPC architecture (close to option 4) as a practical method for achieving interoperability in systems where neither the EMS nor the DERs natively support IEEE 2030.5, using cascaded conversions to bridge multiple protocols while maintaining a scalable publish/subscribe communication model.

The diversity of these implementations confirms that no single deployment model is universally optimal; rather, the InterSTORE interoperability tools can be adapted to a wide range of architectures, from cloud-based flexibility platforms to embedded local control environments. The common integration methodology developed in T3.3 has proven effective in guiding each partner toward a solution that balances latency, resource constraints, scalability, and ease of maintenance. These results provide a replicable framework for future deployments and establish a strong foundation for delivering advanced flexibility services, enabling hybridisation of distributed energy resources, and fostering the wider adoption of open, standard-based communication in the smart grid domain.

6 REFERENCES

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7 LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Main PCS of grid emulation in GridLab.....	21
Table 2: List of transformation in LPC in EMS platform in German Pilot.	51
Table 3: List of references.	57

8 LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Client-server architecture.	9
Figure 2. Presentation of communication scenario possible via IEEE 2030.5 over NATS.....	10
Figure 3. Architecture of legacy protocol converter.....	10
Figure 4. Architecture 1: LPC with multiple energy devices with two NATS.....	12
Figure 5. Architecture 2: Single NATS messaging with multiple LPC within the devices.	13
Figure 6. Architecture 3: Single LPC with multiple NATS.....	14
Figure 7. Architecture 4: Dual LPC with single NATS.	15
Figure 8. Architecture 5: Direct integration of EMS and energy devices with cloud NATS.....	16
Figure 9. Systematic representation of integration of client-server library in CyberNoc.	17
Figure 10. High level architecture of client-server library and LPC in Austrian pilot	18
Figure 11. Presentation of FCC in Austrian Pilot.....	19
Figure 12 Solar panel data gathered via FCC in CyberNoc.....	19
Figure 13. GridLab equipment distribution.....	20
Figure 14. Real system scheme.....	22
Figure 15. HESS Under Test (HUT) configuration.....	23
Figure 16 Mapping in Spanish Gridlab scenario.	26
Figure 17. Final data communication scheme in GridLab.....	27
Figure 18 Testing Scenario - FPS.....	29
Figure 19. Laboratory experimental results of FPS service: Power at the POC and storage output power	29
Figure 20. Laboratory experimental results: comparisons of controller power at the POC: CAN-based method and LPC-based approach.	29
Figure 21. Inverter – Sun characteristics.....	31
Figure 22. Architecture of legacy protocol converter deployment at CapWatt UC05.....	33
Figure 23. Log file example of the results in the Capwatt facilities test.	33
Figure 24. Architecture of the EnelX Pilot for UC09	35
Figure 25. Networking of Field Assets in EnelX Lab and IT platform.....	36
Figure 26. Integration approach selected for Italian Pilot	37
Figure 27. Integration Mapping for Application and Services integration	38
Figure 28. Integration of LPC gateway.....	39
Figure 29.Sunspec Alliance Certificate for XWpro Gateway	39
Figure 30. Integration of IEEE 2030.5 Client-Server	40
Figure 31. Test Logs of handshake process,secure keys exchange to establish Client-Server secure connection	41
Figure 32. IEEE 2030.5 Schneider inverter XWpro client setting.....	41
Figure 33. Test of configuration input/output connections of the LPC for telemetry flow and command flow	42
Figure 34. Verification that the value reported in the Yaml implementation corresponds to value red on Scada system	43
Figure 35. Registration outcome on Device Management Console of IoT platform	43
Figure 36. Infocert registration of LPC gateway in IoT platform	44
Figure 37. Telemetries flow received in IoT platform.....	44
Figure 38. Telemetries flow received in EMS platform	45
Figure 39. EMS load areas configured and flex order is applied.....	45
Figure 40. Eaton SMP 4250 internals: master and slave protocols and real-time data exchange.....	46

Figure 41. Cascaded deployment of LPCs to enable IEEE 2030.5 communication with non-native endpoints..... 48

Figure 42. Eaton EMS platform’s integration to multi-physics hybrid energy storage system in FZJ campus..... 50

Figure 43. LPC configuration for Eaton EMS - connections 52

Figure 44. LPC configuraton for Eaton EMS - transformation for monitoring 53

Figure 45. LPC transformation in Eaton EMS - logging a monitoring instance..... 53

Figure 46. LPC configuration for Eaton EMS - transformation for control 54

Figure 47. LPC transformation in Eaton EMS - logging a control instance (incoming))..... 54

Figure 48. LPC transformation in Eaton EMS - logging a control instance (outgoing)..... 55